

DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF AERO-SPIKE NOZZLE IN ROCKET ENGINE

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Abstract:

For future fully reusable SSTOs and rocket engines, light weight and high performance propulsion system from low altitude to high altitude are essential. A renewed interest into aero-spike (plug) nozzles has surfaced for the possible replacement of standard contoured nozzles used for the propulsion systems of space vehicles. In this project a study of De-Laval nozzle and Aero-spike nozzles characteristic of its flow field is carried out. Numerical analysis of a typical aero-spike and De-Laval nozzle with result analysis and discussion on flow characteristic, comparison on different pressure and temperature ratios are included. The commercial software Ansys-Fluent16.0 is used for the numerical simulation of the problem. Steady state analysis with implicit formulation is carried out. Mass, momentum and energy equations with turbulence model are solved.

Key Words: Plug Nozzle, Turbulence, Momentum & De-Laval Nozzle.

1. Introduction:

Conventional bell nozzle with fixed area ratio works efficiently at a particular altitude where exit pressure exactly matches with the back (ambient) pressure causing exhaust to perfectly expanded thereby maximizing efficiency and thrust. At lower altitude where ambient pressure is higher than the exhaust pressure, the ambient air pushes the exhaust air inward which causes the separation of flow from the boundary of nozzle wall thereby decreasing thrust and efficiency. This condition is also known as overexpansion. At higher altitude where ambient pressure is lower than the exit pressure which is known as under expansion. Ambient air causes exhaust to flow past the nozzle exit. Since the additional expansion occurs outside of the nozzle, the available thrust in the nozzle is lost. Since, both overexpansion and under expansion reduce overall engine efficiency and thrust, for maximizing thrust and efficiency, the concept of an ideal nozzle has been contemplated. An ideal nozzle would be able to continually adjust its area ratio to maximize thrust at each altitude, known as altitude compensation. Practically it is not possible to design a bell nozzle which changes its geometry during the flight. Aero-spike nozzle is an option where the flow is adapted to the ambient conditions at all altitudes, by virtue of the nozzle configuration. In theory at least, the Aero-spike nozzle meets or exceeds the performance of the bell nozzle at all operating pressures. Though the aero-spike nozzle has many advantages such as, uniform load distribution, simple gas dynamic configuration, and flexible structure combinations, the realization of such nozzle faces many hurdles due to its aerodynamic and structural design considerations. The present work hence planned to find the pressure and temperature of the aero-spike nozzle and thrust variation of the aero-spike nozzle. Aero-spike nozzle at varying back pressure conditions which requires the unsteady pressure boundary conditions to be imposed at the outlets. The performance of the nozzle is planned to be analyzed using a computational model which employ an unsteady simulation to account for the varying back pressure conditions to match with the actual flight data.

2. Computational Methodology:

The flow field in ejector is governed by compressible axis symmetric Navier-Stokes equation. The equations below however are written in Cartesian co-ordinates for easiness. In this study Favre averaged NS equations are used because of their pertinence in density varying flows. The equations hence are written below. The turbulence is modelled by modelling the Reynolds stresses. The summary of equations used for this which is given below.

Continuity,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho u_i) = 0$$

Momentum,

$$\rho \frac{D(u_i)}{Dt} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\mu_{eff} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (-\rho \overline{u_i u_j})$$

The velocity here is mean velocity, while the prime components are the disturbance components (due to turbulence) and it denotes Reynolds stresses.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho E) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}[u_i(\rho E + P)] \\ = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left[\left(\alpha + \frac{C_p \mu_j}{P_{r_i}} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} + u_j(\tau_{ij})_{\text{eff}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

E and T are mass averaged, while τ_{ij} is the stress tensor, where

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu_{\text{eff}} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \mu_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} \delta_{ij}$$

The ideal gas equation is also used for balancing the equations with unknown

$$\frac{P}{\rho} = rT$$

The transport equation for Reynolds stress, which are computed for Reynolds stresses in RSM model is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \overline{u_i u_j}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k}(\overline{u_k \rho u_i u_j}) \\ = D_{ij}^T + D_{ij}^L + P_{ij} + \phi_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij} \end{aligned}$$

The right hand side denotes turbulent diffusion, molecular diffusion, stress production, pressure strain, and dissipation respectively, where,

$$D_{ij}^L = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{u_i u_j} \right)$$

$$P_{ij} = -\rho \left(\overline{u_i u_j} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_k} + \overline{u_i u_j} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_k} \right)$$

The equations for other parameters are not known and have to be modelled, the modelled equations are,

$$D_{ij}^T = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} [\rho \overline{u_i u_j u_k} + P(\delta_{kj} u_i + \delta_{ik} u_j)]$$

$$\phi_{ij} = P \overline{\left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)}$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = -2\mu \overline{\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_k} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_k}}$$

Boundary Condition:

An axisymmetric model of the aero-spike nozzle is used to carry out the computations, which is shown in Fig. 1, where the boundary conditions are also shown. The inlet temperature is 1300 K. The outlet temperature 300 K at the ground level, and these vary with the altitude.

Figure 1: Aero-Spike Nozzle

Grid System:

The grid system for the computations is shown in Fig. 2. A grid independence study is also performed for the grid sensitivity to the solution. It can be seen that there is not much variation the critical property if the grid number is changed. From the study, the grid system consisting of 104356 was hence chosen for the computational analysis.

Figure 2: Grid system

3. Results:

A performance analysis has been carried out keeping the velocity inlet as the major parameters, to optimize the geometry. Numerical analysis is done using commercial CFD software ANSYS FLUENT 16.0. The performance of the Aero-spike nozzle is studied for several parameters. The flow properties such as pressure, temperature Mach number etc. are analysed and reported. The complex flow behaviour inside the flow domain is identified using the counters and charts. The fig.3 is mentioned in the static pressure of the convergence divergence nozzle in the flow field.

Figure 3: Pressure Difference

The fig.4 is mentioned the temperature difference of the aero-spike nozzle. The initial temperature is 1300k in the inlet of the Aero-spike nozzle.

Figure 4: Temperature Aero-spike nozzle

Figure 5: Temperature Difference of Aero-spike Nozzle

The fig.6 is mentioned the velocity difference of Aero-Spike nozzle. The velocity is 583.5 m/s in the inlet of the Aero-spike nozzle.

Figure 6: Velocity of the Aero-spike nozzle

3. Conclusion:

A computational study is carried out to study the flow characteristics in an aero-spike nozzle. The computational results are validated with schlieren pictures. The flow characteristics are found to be strong function of the base pressure through ambient pressure which is varying when the rocket ascends. At lower altitudes, and the over expanded plumes form a closed wake at the aero-spike base. The performance of the aero-spike becomes maximum when the nozzle exit pressure equals the ambient pressure at moderately high altitudes. At higher altitudes, the plumes are under expanded and the closed wake zone appears at the base and reduces the performance. Since the thrust is affected by the base pressure, a higher base area is advantageous at higher altitudes to increase the thrust of the aero-spike nozzle.

4. References:

1. Dumnov, G. E., Nikulin, G. Z., and Ponomaryov, N. B., "Investigation of Advanced Nozzles for Rocket Engines," Space Rocket Engines and Power Plants, Vol. 4, No. 142, NIIP, 1993, pp. 10.12 – 10.18.
2. Nguyen, T. V., and Pieper, J. L., "Nozzle Flow Separation," Proceedings of the 5th International Symposium of Propulsion in Space Transportation (Paris, France), 1996.
3. Manski, D., "Clustered Plug Nozzles for Future European Reusable Rocket Launchers," German Aerospace Research Establishment, 643-81/7, Lampoldshausen, Germany, 1981.
4. Immich, H., and Caporicci, M., "FESTIP Technology Developments in Liquid Rocket Propulsion for Reusable Launch Vehicles," AIAA Paper 96-3113, July 1996.